

THE IMPACT OF WEATHER PARAMETERS ON DOWNY MILDEW DISEASE OF BOTTLE GOURD

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Abstract

Downy mildew disease of bottle gourd caused by *Pseudoperonospora cubensis* is one of the most important foliar diseases, causing significant losses in India. Weather factors such as temperature and moisture play a vital role in occurrence, prevalence and spread of downy mildew disease. The correlation and regression study were conducted to find out the influence of weather parameters on the initiation and spread of the downy mildew disease of bottle gourd and develop a suitable weather based disease forecasting equation. The correlation study revealed that downy mildew disease intensity showed positively correlated with maximum temperature (0.065), morning relative humidity (0.451), evening relative humidity (0.033) and evaporation (0.422). Whereas rainfall (-0.519), minimum temperature (-0.319) and wind speed (-0.461) were negatively correlated. rainfall (-0.519*) and wind speed (-0.461*) showed significantly negative correlation and morning relative humidity (0.451*) showed significantly positive correlation with downy mildew disease. Co-efficient of determination R^2 value (0.57) represent than 57.00 per cent influence on the intensity of downy mildew by two independent variables viz., Maximum temperature and Morning relative humidity.

Keywords: Bottle gourd, downy mildew, weather, correlation, regression

Introduction

Bottle gourd (*Lagenaria siceraria* (Mol.) Standl.) is an important cross pollinated monoecious vegetable crop. It belongs to the Cucurbitaceae family with chromosome number $2n = 22$. It is believed to originate in sub-Saharan Africa (Decker-Walters *et al.*, 2004; Erickson *et al.*, 2005) In India bottle gourd area and production are 1.10 lakh ha and production 31.71 lakh tonnes. As regard status of Maharashtra, the area is 303 ha and 5.51 lakh tonnes production (Anonymous 2022). The fruit can be used as vegetable or for making sweets. Bottle gourd is infected by various fungal diseases viz., Downy mildew (*Pseudoperonospora cubensis*), Powdery mildew (*Erysiphe cichoracearum*) and Anthracnose (*Colletotrichum orbiculare*), *Cercospora* leaf spot (*Cercospora citrullina*), *Alternaria* leaf blight (*Alternaria cucumerina*). Among the foliar diseases, downy mildew caused by the oomycetes *Pseudoperonospora cubensis* (Berk & Curt) Rostov is of major economic importance and widely spread plant pathogens in many regions of the World (Palti and Cohen., 1980; Lehmann., 1991; Lebeda and Cohen., 2011). It greatly affects both yield and quality (Rai and Yadav, 2005; Maheshwari *et al.*, 2017). The downy mildew incidence and severity

ranged from 50 to 100 per cent (Sharma *et al.*, 2003). The disease caused by this fungus characterized by first appear as pale green areas on the upper leaf surfaces. These change to yellow angular spots. Grey to purple coloured downy mold growth develops on the undersides of leaves, which is first white and later turns grey-brown. Infected foliage to become necrotic and leading to plant death. Downy mildew can infect wide range of temperatures (6-35°C) but is most severe from (15-20 °C).

Material and methods

The experiment was conducted at the experimental farm of Department of Plant Pathology, College of Agriculture, (VNMKV), Parbhani, Maharashtra. Non replicated trial of bottle gourd cv. Warad was laid out during *Kharif* 2023-24 having a plot size 10 x10 m. The soil type was vertisol. No specific plant protection measures were applied, but all standard agronomic practices were followed throughout the experiment. Observation on per cent disease index (PDI) of downy mildew disease was recorded weekly interval. Ten plants were randomly selected for these observations. The severity of downy mildew was assessed using a disease rating scale ranging from 0 to 5 as described by Metawally and Rakha (2015) in Table A.

Table A: Disease rating scale for downy mildew

Disease Scale	Description
0	No disease
1	0.10-0.15% leaf area affected
2	15.1-25.0% leaf area affected
3	25.1-50.0% leaf area affected
4	50.1-75.0% leaf area affected
5	>75 leaf area affected

Further, the recorded grade values were converted into Per cent disease index (PDI) using formula given by Wheeler (1969).

$$\text{Per cent disease index (\%)} = \frac{\text{Sum of numerical rating}}{\text{No. of plant observed} \times \text{Maximum rating}} \times 100$$

Metrological data viz., rainfall, maximum and minimum temperatures, morning and evening relative humidity, hours of bright sunshine, evaporation and wind velocity during crop's growth period were obtained from the nearby Metrological Observatory of the Department of Agricultural Meteorology, VNMKV, Parbhani.

Statistical analysis

At the end of season, the data obtained were subjected to statistical analysis. The correlation as well as multiple linear regression between weather factors and downy mildew of bottle gourd were estimated. Data was analyzed by OPSTAT statistical data analysis software.

Results and discussion

Per cent disease index (PDI) of downy mildew of bottle gourd obtained at different stages of crop growth were correlated with weather parameters prevailed during the crop season *Kharif* 2023-24. Periodic PDI of downy mildew was recorded at seven days interval in bottle gourd starting from 35th (SMW) i.e. 2nd Sep to 43th (SMW) i.e. 28th Oct till harvest of the crop and the correlation coefficients are presented in Table 1. Among these parameters the downy mildew disease PDI was positively correlated with maximum temperature (0.065), morning relative humidity (0.451), evening relative humidity (0.033) and evaporation (0.422). Whereas, rainfall (-0.519), minimum temperature (-0.319) and wind speed (-0.461) were negatively correlated. rainfall (-0.519*) and wind speed (-0.461*) showed significantly negative correlation and morning relative humidity (0.451*) showed significantly positive correlation with downy mildew disease.

Table 1. Correlation coefficients between the weather parameters and downy mildew of bottle gourd

Weather parameters	Correlation co-efficient “r”
Rainfall (mm)	-0.519*
Maximum Temperature (°C)	0.065
Minimum Temperature(°C)	-0.319
Morning RH (%)	0.451*
Evening RH (%)	0.033
Evaporation (mm)	0.422
Bright sunshine (hrs)	-0.195
Wind speed (km/h)	-0.461*
Note. * p < 0.05	

It is apparent that no one weather condition can have an independent influence on the disease development. The interaction of numerous climatic elements most likely influenced the disease development. Therefore, for multiple linear regression, the stepwise model was

selected and the co-efficient of determination (R^2) was developed for the prediction of downy mildew disease incidence in bottle gourd as given in Table 2.

Table 2: Multiple linear regression equation between disease severity and meteorological factors

R^2	Coefficient of multiple determination	Regression equation
0.57	57.00	$\hat{Y} = -342.883 + 7.519 * X_1 + 1.317 * X_2$ Where, \hat{Y} = Downy mildew disease severity (%) b = Constant (-343.883) X_1 = Maximum Temperature (°C) X_2 = Morning RH (%)

Regression Equation:

Downy mildew disease PDI = -342.883, maximum temperature 7.519*, morning relative humidity 1.317*. The stepwise linear regression analysis revealed that maximum temperature and morning relative humidity were positively correlated with downy mildew severity with R^2 value of 0.57 Co-efficient of multiple determination R^2 value represented that 57.00 per cent influence on the PDI of downy mildew by two independent variables viz., maximum temperature (°C) morning relative humidity (%). These results are in conformity with those reported by Ghosh *et al.* (2015), Daunde *et al.* (2017), Khatal *et al.* (2023).

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